

A novel compartmental Schiff base ligand as a fluorescence chemosensor : Microscopic to macroscopic detection of Zn^{II} acetate

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Abstract : A novel compartmental Schiff base ligand, (L = *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol) serves as a fluorescence chemosensor for the detection of zinc(II) acetate salt. The fluorescent probe (L) undergoes a remarkable fluorescence enhancement upon binding to zinc acetate in pure acetonitrile (MeCN). Interestingly, addition of other 3d-metal acetate salts to the probe, exhibit usual fluorescence quenching phenomenon in MeCN solution. The fluorescent probe (L) can selectively detect Zn^{II} acetate salt in a concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol/L. Further, trinuclear Zn^{II}-Schiff base complex has been characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction study supports the selectivity and binding ability of L with Zn²⁺ ion.

Keywords : Molecular recognition, zinc(II), Schiff base, X-ray structure, fluorescence probe.

Introduction

The creation of organic molecular species having the ability to sense analytes selectively, especially cations, are of biologically and environmentally important and have been emerged as a significant goal in the field of chemical sensors in recent years¹⁻³. Chemical fluoro-sensors which are based on ion-induced fluorescence changes have created huge interests to chemists in terms of sensitivity, selectivity, response time, simplicity, high degree of specificity and low detection limit¹⁻⁴. Fluorescent sensors remain an indispensable tool for visualizing or monitoring metal ions in real-time and real-space at a molecular level without any special instrumentation, and are applicable in many fields such as medical diagnostics, environmental control, living cells, and electronics^{1,4-7}. Zinc is a very important bio-essential element and plays significant roles in the living system effecting, DNA synthesis, microtubule polymerization, gene expression, apoptosis, immune system function, and the activity of different metallo-enzymes such as carbonic anhydrase and matrix metalloproteinase⁸. Moreover, zinc ion is also a

contributory factor in neurological disorders such as epilepsy and Alzheimer's diseases⁹.

Over the past few decades, many fluorescent chemosensors of different class for Zn²⁺ have been developed, using quinoline¹⁰, anthracene¹¹ and coumarin¹² as fluorophores. However, some of them require complicated syntheses and are insoluble in aqueous medium. Further, various fluorescence-based zinc probes have been recently developed – some of these are fluorescent adducts of Zn-chelating peptides¹³⁻¹⁵ and proteins¹⁶, while others are dye adducts of Zn-chelating macrocyclic compounds¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Although some of these fluorescent probes can be utilized to detect zinc ions in environmental or biological samples, they have serious disadvantages like insufficient selectivity or sensitivity. Schiff bases (SBs) have the potential to form stable complexes of varied nuclearities with transition metal ions and act as ion carriers. The feature of SBs gives geometric and cavity control of host-guest complexation and modulation of its lipophilicity, and produces remarkable selectivity, sensitivity and stability for a specific ion. Thus, in this present report a novel

compartmental Schiff base ligand, (**L** = *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol), Scheme 1, is used as an ionophore with N and O donor atoms for construction of a Zn^{II} chemosensor. Further, a trinuclear Zn^{II}-Schiff base complex is characterized in the form of single crystals in MeCN medium with an external addition of little amount of DMF, and this phenomenon supports and consolidates the selectivity and efficient binding ability of **L** with Zn²⁺ ion in a 2 : 3 binding manner.

Results and discussion

Syntheses and formulation of the Schiff base (**L**)

The Schiff base ligand, **L**, *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol was synthesized by condensing 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol with 2-salicylaldehyde in 1 : 2 molar ratio in dry ethanol following a reported procedure²⁰. The formulation was confirmed by elemental analysis, IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR, and ESI-MS spectral analysis. The schematic presentation of synthesis is given below :

Scheme 1. Preparative procedure of the Schiff base (**L**).

Photophysical and solution properties of **L**

The photophysical study and the structural integrity in solution state for the Schiff base ligand (**L**) has been examined by proton NMR, UV-Vis spectroscopy, fluorescence study and ESI mass spectral studies. The ligand is soluble in common organic solvents like methanol, acetonitrile, dichloromethane etc. The ¹H NMR spectral data for this Schiff base compound is provided in Experimental section and accounts in favour of the formulation of **L**. The UV-Vis spectrum for **L** shows high intensity transitions in the range of 200 to 500 nm (Fig. 1). The Schiff base solution shows the

characteristic absorption bands at 316, 363 and 414 nm in acetonitrile solvent (10^{-4} M; Fig. 1). The highly intense band at 316 nm is assigned to π - π^* transition of the C=N chromophore, whereas the band with low intensity at 363 nm is due to n - π^* transition and a broad band \sim 414 nm is appeared for intraligand charge transfer²¹ (Fig. 1). The fluorescence spectral measurement for receptor, **L** in the absence of any divalent metal ions was carried out in acetonitrile using 10^{-4} M at room temperature and the spectrum is also given in Fig. 1. The ligand, excited at 363 nm, have shown emission band around 424 nm. The lower fluorescence intensity of **L** may be attributed for losing of co-planarity.

In order to probe the solution stability of **L**, ESI-MS spectrum in acetonitrile solution at room temperature is taken. It consolidates the solution stability of **L** which exhibits the molecular ion peak as base peak at m/z 299.17 in acetonitrile medium. ESI-MS (MeCN) m/z 299.17 [**L**+H⁺] (Calcd. 299.13).

Fluorogenic Zn^{II}-acetate recognition

To establish the practical applications, the fluorescence response behavior of the ligand was examined upon addition of 3d divalent metal acetate in acetonitrile medium. Fig. 2 shows the fluorescence intensity of **L** in the presence of different metal acetates. Only Zn-salts resulted in a pronounced fluorescence enhancement, whereas other transition metal salts including Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺ did not change fluorescence (Fig. 3) even at concentrations 10-fold higher than the corresponding Zn²⁺ ion concentration as there is a probability of an electron and energy transfer be-

Fig. 1. Left : UV-Vis spectrum of **L** in MeCN; Right : Fluorescence spectrum of **L** in MeCN ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 363$ nm).

Fig. 2. Fluorescence titration of **L** (1×10^{-6} M) in MeCN medium upon addition of different divalent late 3d acetate solution of 1×10^{-6} M concentration ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 363$ nm). Inset : Visual fluorescence changes of sensor **L** in the presence of zinc acetate. The photo was taken under a hand held UV (365 nm) lamp.

tween the metal ion and ligands²² or quenching of fluorescence intensity of a ligand by transition metal ions during complexation is a rather common phenomenon which is explained by processes such as magnetic perturbation, redox-activity, electronic energy transfer, etc.²³. When the experiment was carried out with ubiquitous intracellular metal ions such as K^+ ,

Fig. 3. 3D bar diagram of fluorescence intensity of **L** (1×10^{-6} M) in MeCN with different 3d acetate solution.

Na^+ and Ca^{2+} , which exist at very high concentrations inside the cell, no significant fluorescence was observed, even at concentrations that were 100-fold higher than Zn^{2+} ion concentration. However, treatment of various zinc(II) salts like chloride, nitrate, sulphate, bisulphate, phosphate with **L** exhibit similar kind of enhancement of fluorescence intensity. Enhancement of fluorescence through complexation is,

however, of much interest as it opens up the window for photochemical applications of the metal complexes^{24,25}. Factors like a simple binding of ligand to the d^{10} metal ions²⁵, an increased rigidity in structure of the complexes²⁶, a restriction in the photoinduced electron transfer (PET)^{24,27}, etc. are assigned to the increase in the photoluminescence. For this case, the enhancement of fluorescence intensity may be accounted by considering the imposed rigidity through complexation and decrement of the non-radiative decay of the excited-state with increasing radiative decay.

The photophysical responses of the Schiff base ligands are modulated when the fluorophore and the guest binding units are covalently integrated, resulting in a possible excited-state electron transfer phenomenon between the two. This can be termed as a Zn^{2+} ion selective chelation enhanced fluorescence. The experiment shows that there is a significant increase in fluorescence intensity for **L** upon addition of zinc(II) acetate salt. The emission peak intensity of **L** at 424 nm upon successive addition of zinc acetate concomitantly increases (Fig. 4) whether excited at 363 nm. Other salts of zinc(II) ion can enhance the fluorescence intensity of the **L** but the extent of enhancement is

Fig. 4. Fluorescence titration of **L** (1×10^{-6} M) in MeCN medium upon successive addition of Zn-acetate solution of 1×10^{-6} M concentration (Excitation wavelength, 316 nm or 363 nm).

significantly small compared to the acetate salt. At least 2–3 fold more enhancement of fluorescence intensity is observed for the acetate salt compared to other zinc(II) salts. Thus, it is concluded that the Zn^{2+} ion selectively in a concentration range from 10^{-6} (M) to 10^{-4} (M) in acetonitrile medium using **L** as a fluorescence chemosensor.

Isolation of zinc-L complex in macroscopic scale

In order to evaluate the coordination nature of **L** to a Zn^{2+} ion, Zn^{2+} -**L** complex is isolated and crystallized. Simple mixing of zinc acetate and **L**, instantly produced crystalline colourless compounds. But successful isolation of single crystals, external addition of little amount of DMF is very much essential. Different ratios of zinc acetate and **L** are used (10^{-2} M each) to isolate monomeric or dimeric or trimeric or polymeric Zn-L complex, but obtained beautiful colourless crystals of rectangular shape when 3 : 2 Zn-acetate and **L** molar proportion is used. In this synthesis, acetate ions have contributed as bridging units to bind adjacent zinc ions together. The coordination geometry of trinuclear zinc(II) complex, $[Zn_3(L)_2(OAc)_2] \cdot 2DMF$ was determined by mainly single crystal X-ray diffraction study along with different spectroscopic and analytical techniques.

Description of crystal structure

The X-ray structural determination of $[Zn_3(L)_2(OAc)_2] \cdot 2DMF$ reveals a trinuclear neutral zinc(II) complex with the space group $P\bar{1}$. The compound has been found to have a trinuclear molecule with a central Zn^{II} ion lying on a center of inversion. An ORTEP view²⁸ of μ -acetato- μ -phenoxo-trizinc(II) complex of $[Zn_3(L)_2(OAc)_2] \cdot 2DMF$ with an atom labelling scheme is shown in Fig. 5. The crystallographic parameter for the compound is given in Table 1. The trinuclear complex is built up of two mononuclear Zn-L moieties linked through bridging acetate and μ_2 -phenolato groups to the central Zn atom. The coordination geometry around the terminal Zn centers (Zn1 and Zn1ⁱ) may be regarded as square pyramidal geom-

Fig. 5. Bond line view of the X-ray structure of the trinuclear zinc(II)-Schiff base complex.

etry where the equatorial plane of a terminal Zn1/Zn1ⁱ atom is formed by phenoxo-bridged oxygen (O2/O2ⁱ), phenoxo oxygen (O1/O1ⁱ), imine nitrogen (N3/N3ⁱ), imine nitrogen (N4/N4ⁱ) and the axial positions are occupied by acetato bridged oxygen (O3/O3ⁱ). However, the coordination geometry of the central zinc ion (Zn2) may also be best described as distorted octahedral geometry, formed by six oxygen atoms from the same Schiff base ligands and bridging acetate ions which coordinate the terminal zinc ions. Thus four phenoxo-oxygen (O1/O1ⁱ, O2/O2ⁱ) from two Schiff base ligands and two acetate ions bridge the two terminal zinc ions (Zn1 and Zn1ⁱ) and the central zinc ion (Zn2). The four equatorial positions for terminal zinc ions (Zn1 and Zn1ⁱ) are occupied by two phenoxo oxygen atoms (O2/O2ⁱ, O1/O1ⁱ) and two imine nitrogen atoms (N3/N3ⁱ, N4/N4ⁱ) where as the central zinc ion is surrounded by four phenoxo-bridged oxygen atom (O1, O1ⁱ, O2, O2ⁱ) from the two Schiff base ligands. Axial positions for all three zinc ions are coordinated by acetate bridged oxygen atom (O3, O4, O4ⁱ, O3ⁱ). The three zinc ions are in a perfect linear arrangement ($\angle\text{Zn1-Zn2-Zn1}^i = 180.0^\circ$). The distances between the central zinc ion (Zn2) and the two terminal zinc ions (Zn1/Zn1ⁱ) are 3.061(1) Å.

Table 1. Crystallographic data of $[\text{Zn}_3\text{L}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2]$

Crystal parameters	Zn-L complex
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{50}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{12}\text{Zn}_3$
Formula weight	1049.87
Temperature	293(2) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	$P\bar{1}$
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 9.5022(12)$ Å $\alpha = 66.820(18)^\circ$, $b = 10.5453(15)$ Å $\beta = 78.47(3)^\circ$, $c = 13.0143(8)$ Å $\gamma = 89.67(3)^\circ$
Volume	$1170.8(3)$ Å ³
Z	1
Density (Calcd.)	1.433 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	1.586 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	520
Theta range for data collection	1.7 to 27.5°
Index ranges	$-12 \leq h \leq 12$, $-13 \leq k \leq 13$, $-16 \leq l \leq 16$
Reflections collected	12711
Independent reflections	10199
R(int)	0.106
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	0.99
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	R1 = 0.1093, wR2 = 0.3635
Largest diff. peak and hole	1.26 and -0.98 e. Å ⁻³

Conclusion

Herein, I report a novel compartmental Schiff base ligand as a fluorescence chemosensor for the detection of zinc(II) acetate salt. The fluorescent probe (**L**) undergoes enhancement of fluorescence emission intensity upon binding to zinc acetate or any zinc^{II} salts in MeCN while addition of other 3d-metal acetate salts to the probe, exhibit usual fluorescence quenching phenomenon in MeCN solution. The fluorescent probe (**L**) can selectively detect Zn^{II} acetate salt in a concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol/L. Further, isolation of trinuclear zinc-Schiff base complex, $[\text{Zn}_3(\text{L})_2(\text{OAc})_2] \cdot 2\text{DMF}$ in the form of single crystals

in MeCN medium with an external addition of DMF supports and consolidates the selectivity and binding ability of **L** with Zn^{2+} ion in 2 : 3 ratio. Thus this compartmental Schiff base, **L** can effectively and selectively recognize Zn^{2+} ion in a mixture of other bivalent 3d ions and behaves an efficient fluorescence chemosensor from micro to macro scale of concentration.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity salisaldehyde (E. Merck, India), 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol (Lancaster, UK), methylene blue (Aldrich, UK), zinc(II) acetate dihydrate (E. Merck, India), copper(II) acetate dihydrate (E. Merck, India), nickel(II) acetate (E. Merck, India), cobalt(II) acetate dihydrate (E. Merck, India), manganese(II) acetate dihydrate (E. Merck, India) and iron(II) acetate dihydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. All the other reagents and solvents are of analytical grade (A.R. grade) and were purchased from commercial sources and used as received.

Physical measurements :

Infrared spectrum (KBr) was recorded with a FTIR-8400S Shimadzu spectrophotometer in the range 400–3600 cm^{-1} . 1H NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 was obtained on a Bruker Avance 300 MHz spectrometer at 25 °C and was recorded at 299.948 MHz. Chemical shifts are reported with reference to SiMe₄. Ground state absorption was measured with a JASCO V-730 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Hitachi F-7000 fluorescence spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN microanalyser.

Preparation of **L** and zinc(II) complex :

Salisaldehyde (0.244 g, 2 mmol) was heated under reflux with 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol (0.089 g, 1 mmol) in 30 ml dehydrated alcohol. After 10 h the reaction solution was evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a gummy mass, which was dried under vacuum and

stored over $CaCl_2$ for subsequent use. Yield : 0.278 g (82.8%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{18}N_2O_3$ (**L**) : C, 68.48; H, 6.08; N, 9.39. Found : C, 68.40; H, 6.02; N, 9.35; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 3.68 (2H, dd, $J=12.4$, 6.8 Hz), 3.84 (2H, dd, $J=12.4$, 4.0 Hz), 4.23–4.25 (1H, m), 6.88 (2H, t, $J=7.2$ Hz), 6.96 (2H, d, $J=8.4$ Hz), 7.25 (2H, dd, $J=7.6$, 1.6 Hz), 7.32 (2H, td, $J=8.8$, 1.6 Hz), 8.36 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR δ : 62.9, 70.2, 117.0, 118.5, 118.6, 131.5, 132.5, 161.1, 167.3 ppm; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1634, 1611 ($\nu_{C=N}$), 3412 (ν_{OH}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) : ~316, 363, 424 nm.

An acetonitrile solution of $Zn(OAc)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.657 g, 3 mmol) (10 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of **L** (0.596 g, 2 mmol) in the same solvent (15 ml). The yellow solution of the ligand immediately became colourless with quick precipitation of white crystalline compound. It was filtered and recrystallized from acetonitrile-dimethyl formamide (DMF) solvent mixture. The solvent mixture produced colourless crystals. Yield : 0.453 g (69% based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{38}N_4O_{10}Zn_3$ (**1**) : C, 50.32; H, 4.22; N, 6.18. Found : C, 50.40; H, 4.27; N, 6.27%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3436 (ν_{OH}), 1634, 1605 ($\nu_{C=N}$), 1497, 1460, 1420 (ν_{OAc}), 1276 (ν_{PhO}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) : 266, 361.

X-Ray diffraction study :

Single crystal X-ray diffraction data were collected using a Rigaku XtaLABmini diffractometer equipped with Mercury CCD detector. The data were collected with graphite monochromated Mo- $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 295(2) K using ω scans. The data were reduced using Crystal Clear suite and the space group determination was done using Olex2. The structure was resolved by direct method and refined by full-matrix least-squares procedures using the SHELXL-97 software package using Olex2 suite^{28,29}.

Zn^{2+} sensing experiments :

The spectral analyses display an excellent chemosensory response both in absorption and fluorescence of

the Schiff base ligand upon addition of trace amounts of zinc acetate in acetonitrile solution. The selectivity of receptor for Zn²⁺ ion over other 3d cations was studied in detail.

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